

QUALITY EDUCATION IN JOURNALISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: the article talks about the proposals and their importance for bringing the system of training in the field of journalism to a new level in Uzbekistan. Also, the problems and issues of the current situation are considered.

Keywords : journalism, journalism education, grants, journalists, education, achieving quality education

Education this is development basis. In fields development education quality set will give. But this all directions for same, education strategy working the concept does not give. This is journalism in the field teaching methodology and can also be seen in the program. Journalism in society the fourth is power . That's why it is field personnel teaching separately program and attention Demand will do". ¹Journalism education development about Europe scientists the most first practice and of theory acceptable the point to find attention they look This practice Uzbekistan higher education institutions are also wide application to do it is necessary. Today's in the day in Uzbekistan journalism according to his own bachelor and master's stage present about 10 higher education institution if , in them practice processes second level to stage down the rest Only one Bukhara state university journalism direction students for total 1 course during 1 month continuous and from class after mandatory didn't happen practice processes app did And this qualified journalists growing in release the problem giving birth can "Fig or volume how from being strict look, journalism education everyone in the place traditional respectively one from the side practical skills teaching, second from the side while common contextual education and liberal arts courses cover takes" ². But Uzbekistan universities in programs

¹"Global journalism education ", Mark Deuze University of Amsterdam

²"Global journalism education ", Mark Deuze University of Amsterdam

theory initial courses during priority degree come back student there is theories to practice current in doing the problem is giving birth. That's why journalism education processes pedagogical education direction program current did without 4 days reading and 2 days of practice mode before need to push. Or lessons weight reduced without each daily 50/50 practice and theory style apply to the goal is appropriate. Also current system during of students journalism theory with engage in indicator increasingly low rate note is doing This is short practice in the process financial incentives through to work interest increased students to practice there is attention directed without own activities continue is making" Public information tools system to himself special needs and requirements from the region to the region difference if he does and basically the law and in history to himself special culture and basis with is determined (and their the opposite although practical and contextual knowledge between thin balance each always main task being came.)" ³That's it in terms of journalism in the field regional or territorial journalism theory development for student theory and his in their research save stay, them this in the direction their research increase it is necessary. In these processes journalism education financing from the way use to the goal is appropriate China. Journalism education in crisis. First, it is still work market requirements answer give can't Second, one series professional or in schools a journalist has been academic instructors not enough Thirdly, professors and teachers scientific research many new organize done in programs faster should develop. Fourth, different journalism schools offer doing study programs essentially one different being them differentiate for unique trade points no. That's it despite Russia pedagogical community today in the day whole to the world special has been book of the team main concerns must understand. The first is industry and of the academy opposite requirements is balancing. Many in chapters public information tools employees journalism teachers field to the dynamics attention without giving, excessively except a lot theory and ideology what they taught for criticism to do said. Other from the side of the university many colleagues journalism programs" trade schools as" they look like that useful didn't happen academic value there ⁴is. Such problem for solution way while Europe in

³"Global journalism education ", Mark Deuze University of Amsterdam

⁴ [Goodman & Stein, 2017, p. 431]

practice applied of journalism himself for grants separate and investors attraction to do to the goal is appropriate .

In this regard USA practice attention deserves. In this country different charity organizations journalism to education spends money. They are each year universities and belongs to organizations suitable coming education initiatives support for allocate millions of dollars. So, Henry Sanchez and Kob Fund 2009-2011 between journalism education grant gift in the amount of 146.4 million dollars did Two fund 2005 and 2011 21st century journalism in between to education about views work exit for allocated nearly 20 million dollars. High to education state by separable funds decrease because of journalism education to the field about financing with one in line grants and contracts at the expense of financial support is increasing important importance occupation is doing That's it addition to do American savings should be the first in line contact fundamentally difference who does digital period for education supports.⁵ This practice and processes Uzbekistan journalism to education app to do in the field happy education formation for the ground creates

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⁵[Goodman & Stein , 2017, p. 227, 228]

